

Seasonal Daylight Saving Time in US: our response letter to their response letter

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Rishi *et al.* (2024b) is a position statement, issued by the American Academy of Sleep Medicine, supporting permanent Standard Time in United States published January 1 2024. We responded with a Letter to the Editor (Martín-Olalla and Mira, 2024) accepted on January 17 2024 and published soon afterwards.

Rishi *et al.* (2024a) is a Letter to the Editor responding to our response letter. We here offer a response to their response.

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Dear Dr. Muhammad A. Rishi, Dr. Jocelyn Y. Cheng, Dr. Andrew Spector,

We greatly appreciate your interest and kindness in responding to our Letter to the Editor. We apologize for the delay in our reply, as we only recently became aware of your response.

We urge you to read our recent Letter in response to a position statement by the British Sleep Society. (Martín-Olalla and Mira, 2025)¹ The history of seasonal clocks in

the UK and US is quite similar, so our arguments there apply to your position statement as well.

In your response letter, you acknowledge the main issue we raised: your position statement lacks balance. After reading your response, our objection remains.

You introduce a new issue associated with seasonal clocks: energy saving. This leads to a simple cost-benefit analysis: the practice must be discontinued because the benefits it brings—unspecific energy saving—cannot outweigh its costs—health issues. This is a common argument in this topic.

It is hard to say “no” to such a balance, which is followed in the response letter by opposing “economic forces” (the evil) and “public health and safety objectives” (the good).

Nonetheless, to us, this balance and this Manichean

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¹ This Letter is also posted as a pre-print under doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14064916

scheme is a source of confusion. Historically, seasonal clocks were not conceived to save energy. Rather, energy saving is a by-effect of the aims and goals of the practice, which the sponsors highlighted so that the government eventually took action in 1916.(Willet, 1907)

Seasonal clocks were conceived to keep the alignment of work hours close to sunrise and to promote greater use of outdoor recreation.(Hudson, 1895, 1898) The first point is, by nature, associated with one of the three clocks you list in your position statement: unlike mechanical clocks, people seldom track the solar culmination (solar noon); instead, people [our photoreceptive mechanisms] track the morning light (sunrise). Seasonal DST helps the social clock to track sunrise, albeit imperfectly. The second item adapts to a social rule of thumb: “duty first, before pleasure.” Mornings and afternoons can grow equally in spring-summer at 40°, but this rule of thumb cannot follow this scheme. Instead, we shift duty more into the morning, but only when morning light allows it (spring and summer).

The sponsors of DST promised greater use of outdoor recreation, and the practice eventually delivered it. People in London and New York loved the new setting in the 1920s, to the point that clocks were never reset to ST during the summer season. This is in stark contrast to what happened after permanent DST was tested in 1969-1970 (UK) and 1973 (US): it was quickly discontinued. Aside from “economic forces” and “health forces,” we see here human preferences: people used to, say, 9am to 5pm work hours, easily welcomed the 8am to 4pm setting in summer (rendered as 9am to 5pm DST), but rejected 8am to 4pm (9am to 5pm DST) in winter.

We never said or suggested that seasonal DST must continue because it is a tradition, therefore we do not feel at all touched by Twain’s words. We put forward that DST helped to solve a problem in the 1920s—the alignment of work hours to sunrise—and that its long-standing persistence is telling. Using the card of “economic forces” as a scapegoat does not help address the problem from a scientific, physiological, or health perspective.

We did not assert that “we should maintain biannual clock change because of its popularity” or anything like that. We addressed an argument by you which roughly runs as follows: since permanent DST was quickly discontinued, the US should embrace permanent ST. We just noted that permanent ST was also quickly and easily discontinued.

With the continued record of alternating clocks in the US and elsewhere, with people having opposing interests—many loving their current summer time schedule, some rejecting the dark mornings of winter—with artificial light playing increasing roles in the dark hours of the winter morning, aside from Manichean arguments and after having opened a Pandora’s box, what if seasonal DST is still the best compromise we can get in

practical terms at 40° latitude to make comfortable those who love early activity and those who love late activity?

Yours sincerely.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

All authors contributed equally to this work.

DECLARATION OF INTEREST

The authors declare no competing interest.

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MANUSCRIPT TIME LINE

We learned of the Letter response on November 18 2024 after checking the citations to our Letter to the Editor and committed to offer a response. Sadly, due to the long time elapsed since the publication of Rishi *et al.* (2024a) journal submission is not an option.